

BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF MANDARIN ORANGE IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

N S Athole*, N V Shende**, N T Bagde*** and S V Warade****

* Master of Business Administration in Agri-Business Management, School of Agri-business Management, Nagpur.

**Head Department of Agricultural Economics & Statistics, Dr.P.D.K.V. Akola

***Associate Professor, College of Agriculture, Akola.

**** Associate Professor (CAS), School of Agri-Business Management, Nagpur.

namanathole7304@gmail.com

MS Received: 03.08.2024; MS Revised:28.04.2024; MS Accepted:29.08.2024)

MS 3230

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRI-BUSINESS MANAGEMENT)

Abstract

India is one of the largest producers of fruits globally, and mandarin oranges (*Citrus reticulata*) hold significant economic importance, particularly in Maharashtra's Vidarbha region. Maharashtra known as the "Orange City." The research aims to identify the different supply chain models, compare price spreads, and evaluate marketing efficiency while addressing the challenges faced by producers and consumers. The study, conducted from 2023 to 2024, employs primary data collection from 20 farmers, 10 consumers, and 5 retailers for each supply chain model. The analysis reveals distinct differences in marketing costs, price spreads, and efficiency across the three supply chains: 1) Traditional Supply Chain: Producers receive a net price of ₹1,191.83 per quintal, with a price spread of ₹3,227.03. Marketing efficiency is 0.35, indicating lower efficiency with high costs for intermediaries. Major issues include price volatility, labour shortages, and high transportation costs. 2) Cooperative Supply Chain: Producers benefit from a higher net price of ₹1,557.82 per quintal and a price spread of ₹3,204.06. This model shows better marketing efficiency at 0.48 due to reduced marketing costs and the involvement of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs). Problems include fewer issues with labour and intermediaries but persistent concerns with high prices and market access. 3) Modern Supply Chain: The net price received by producers is ₹1,185.49 per quintal, with the highest price spread of ₹3,629.29. The marketing efficiency is the lowest at 0.31, affected by higher retail costs. Challenges include high costs related to packaging, waxing, and storage, alongside slow checkout processes for consumers. Consumer problems are also assessed, with high prices relative to quality being a consistent issue across all supply chains. Other consumer concerns vary, with the Traditional Supply Chain showing issues with weighing and grading, while the Modern Supply Chain faces challenges with checkout processes and refilling. The study highlights that while the Cooperative Supply Chain offers better marketing efficiency and producer returns, all models face significant challenges that impact both producers and consumers. Improvements in supply chain practices and infrastructure could enhance efficiency and address these issues, promoting the growth of the mandarin orange industry in India.

Keywords: Supply Chain, Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin, Price Spread, Marketing Efficiency

Introduction

India, known for its agricultural diversity, stands as the second-largest producer of fruits globally, contributing over 10% to world production. The fruit sector is a vital part of the country's agricultural landscape, supporting nutrition, employment, and the economy. Among the various fruits cultivated, mandarin oranges (*Citrus reticulata*), commonly known as Nagpuri Santra, hold significant importance due to their nutritional value and economic contribution. Originating from the Himalayan slopes and regions of Burma and China, mandarin oranges thrive in the tropical and subtropical climates of India, 20-21, accounting for 3% of the world's total production.

In India, the Vidarbha region, particularly Nagpur, is a major hub for mandarin orange cultivation, earning it the title "Orange City." With two primary cropping seasons—Ambe Bahar and Mrig Bahar—the region produces a substantial volume of oranges, which are primarily consumed domestically. The limited export percentage highlights strong internal demand and challenges in meeting international standards, but the growing industrial applications of citrus fruits and their health benefits offer significant opportunities for expansion.

The citrus industry plays a crucial role in India's horticultural landscape, ranking third after mangoes and bananas. Despite its limited export volume, it supports millions of farmers and is poised for further growth through improved production techniques, better infrastructure, and enhanced export strategies. As India continues to develop its agricultural capabilities, the mandarin orange industry is expected to play an increasingly significant role in the global fruit market.

Objective

1. To identify the various supply chain in mandarin orange.
2. To compare the price spread and the market efficiency of various supply chain.
3. To identify the problem faced by producer and consumer.

Materials and Methods

The study, conducted in 2023-2024, focuses on primary data collection in Nagpur district, Maharashtra, known for its high concentration of mandarin orange production. It compares three distinct supply chain models: Traditional, Cooperative, and Modern. The sample size for each model includes 20 farmers, 10 consumers, and 5 retailers,

particularly in Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, and the northeastern states.

Mandarin oranges are highly valued for their rich content of vitamins C, A, and B, along with essential minerals like calcium and phosphorus, making them an important part of a balanced diet. These fruits are consumed both fresh and in processed forms, such as juice, jams, and cosmetics, contributing to their growing demand in both domestic and international markets. India is the ninth-largest producer of mandarin oranges globally, producing 10.5 million tons in 20

ensuring a well-rounded analysis. In the Cooperative Supply Chain, an additional Farmer Producer Organization (FPO) was included to assess its role in supporting farmers. Data collection was done systematically, covering all areas under mandarin cultivation, providing a comprehensive and reliable analysis of the supply chains.

Price Spread

Price spread refers to the difference between the net price received by the farmer (producer price) and the price paid by the consumer for the produce.

Price Spread = Consumer Price - Producer Price

Marketing Efficiency Index (ME)

The Marketing Efficiency Index measures the ratio of the net price received by the producer to the total marketing cost and total net margins of intermediaries, as suggested by Acharya and Agarwal (1998).

$$ME = (FP) / (MC + MM)$$

Where:

ME = Marketing Efficiency

FP = Net price received by the producer

MC = Total Marketing Cost

MM = Total Net Margins of intermediaries

Market Margin

Market Margin = Purchase Price of Individual – Selling Price of Individual

Marketing Cost

Marketing Cost = Marketing Cost incurred by Producer + Marketing Cost incurred by Commission Agent + Marketing Cost incurred by Retailer

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Supply Chain in Mandarin Orange

There are three type of supply chain in mandarin orange

4.1.1 Traditional Supply Chain

The Traditional Supply Chain involves the upstream and downstream relationships with:

Farmer → Pre-Harvester Contractor → Wholesaler Cum Commission Agent → Retail Format → Customer

4.1.2 Cooperative Supply Chain

The Cooperative Supply Chain involves the upstream and downstream relationships with:

Farmer → Cooperative Unit → Wholesaler → Retail Format → Customer

4.1.3 Modern Supply Chain

The Modern Supply Chain involves the upstream and downstream relationships with:

Farmer → Pre-Harvester Contractor → Wholesaler → Consolidation Centre → Retail Format → Customer

4.2 Marketing Cost of Three Supply Chain of Mandarin Orange.

Table No 1 The Marketing Cost of Mandarin Orange in Nagpur District in Three Supply Chain

Marketing Cost Incurred by Producer (Quantity in Quintal)			
	Traditional Supply Chain (Rs)	Cooperative Supply Chain (Rs)	Modern Supply Chain (Rs)
Selling Price	1324.25	2003.70	1317.15
Picking Cost	0.00	135.35	0.00
Loading Charges	0.00	56.90	0.00
Transportation Charges	0.00	123.00	0.00
Weight Charges	0.00	0.75	0.00
Unloading Charges	0.00	29.70	0.00
Vehicle Charges	0.00	0.00	0.00
Marketing Committee Charges (Bazar Entry Fee)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Discount To Company or FPO OR Any Other	0.00	0.00	0.00
Losses	0.00	100.19	0.00
Commission To Pre Harvester 10%	132.43	0.00	131.72
Total	132.43	445.89	131.72
Net Price Received by Producer	1191.83	1557.82	1185.44
Marketing Cost Incurred by Pre-Harvest Contractor (Expect Cooperative has FPO) (Quantity in Quintal)			
Purchase Price of Pre-Harvest Contractor	1191.83	2003.70	1185.44
Picking Charges	135.35	0.00	135.00
Loading Charges	40.00	0.00	40.00
Transportation Charges	125.50	0.00	123.00
Weight Charges	0.75	0.00	0.74
Unloading Charges	25.00	0.00	25.00
Vehicle Charges	1.50	0.00	1.65
Marketing Committee Charges (Bazaar Entry Fee): Rs.	19.90	0.00	19.85
Commission Taken by Wholesaler 6%	71.51	0.00	71.13
Losses	59.59	0.00	59.27
Grading /Sorting	0.00	200.00	0.00
Storage Charges	0.00	0.00	0.00
Any Other Fees	0.00	150.00	0.00
Total	479.10	350.00	475.64
Margin	175.00	20.07	175.00
Selling Price	1845.93	2373.73	1836.08
Marketing Cost Incurred by Wholesaler (Quantity in Quintal)			
Purchase Price of Wholesaler	1845.93	2373.73	1836.08
Labour Charges	121.00	100.00	108.00
Loading Charges	30.00	30.00	30.00
Transport Charges	148.00	150.00	148.00
Unloading Charges	20.00	20.00	20.00
Weight Charges	0.76	0.76	0.76

Discount To Retailer	92.30	118.68	91.80
License Charges	10.00	10.00	10.00
Storage Charges	0.00	0.00	0.00
Packing/Sorting/Grading	165.00	0.00	165.00
Losses	184.59	118.68	183.61
Any Other	206.00	200.00	211.00
Total	977.65	748.13	968.17
Margin	251.00	251.00	251.00
Selling Price of Wholesaler	3074.58	3372.86	3055.25
Marketing Cost Incurred by Retailer (Quantity in Quintal)			
Purchasing Price of Retailer:	3074.58	3372.86	3055.25
Labour Charges:	4.50	4.50	46.60
License Charges:	0.00	0.00	0.00
Shop Charges:	47.60	47.60	47.60
Transportation Charges:	121.00	121.00	121.00
Consolidation Centre (Central Processing Centre)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Storage Charges	0.00	0.00	198.00
Waxing	0.00	0.00	178.00
Packing Charges:	10.00	10.00	10.00
Losses	307.45	337.28	305.52
Discount To Consumer	153.72	168.64	152.76
Miscellaneous Charges	200.00	200.00	200.00
Total: Rs.	844.28	751.18	1259.48
Margin	500.00	500.00	500.00
Total	4418.86	4761.89	4814.78

The marketing costs for mandarin oranges vary across the Traditional, Cooperative, and Modern supply chains, impacting the overall price at different stages. In the Traditional Supply Chain, producers receive a net price of ₹1,191.83 per quintal after incurring marketing costs of ₹132.43, including a 10% commission to pre-harvesters. The Cooperative Supply Chain shows a higher net price of ₹1,557.82 due to additional costs such as picking, loading, and losses, while the Modern Supply Chain results in a net price of ₹1,185.44, with similar pre-harvester commissions. Pre-harvest contractors in the Traditional and Modern chains have higher marketing costs (around ₹479 and

₹475 per quintal) compared to ₹350 in the Cooperative model, where the FPO handles key operations. Wholesalers across all chains incur marketing costs between ₹748 and ₹977 per quintal, with consistent margins of ₹251. Retailers, in turn, face the highest costs in the Modern Supply Chain (₹1,259.48 per quintal) due to added expenses like waxing, storage, and higher losses, whereas the Cooperative model has lower marketing costs (₹751.18). Retailer margins remain the same at ₹500 across all chains, resulting in final selling prices ranging from ₹4,418.86 to ₹4,814.78.

4.3 To Study the Price Spread and Marketing Efficiency of Mandarin Orange in Nagpur District.

Table No 2 The Price Spread and Marketing Efficiency in Three Supply Chain in Mandarin Orange

Sr No	Particulars	Traditional Supply Chain	Cooperative Supply Chain	Modern Supply Chain
		Cost (Percent)	Cost (Percent)	Cost (Percent)
1	Farmer			
	Selling Price	1324.25 (29.97)	2003.70 (42.08)	1317.20 (27.36)
	Marketing Cost	132.43 (3.00)	445.88 (9.36)	131.72 (2.74)
	Net Price Received	1191.83 (26.97)	1557.82 (32.71)	1185.49 (24.62)
2	Pre Harvester (Expect Cooperative Has FPO)			
	Purchase Price	1191.83 (26.97)	2003.70 (42.08)	1185.49 (24.62)
	Marketing Cost	479.10 (10.84)	350.00 (7.35)	475.64 (9.88)
	Margin	175.00 (3.96)	20.03 (0.42)	175.00 (3.63)

3	Wholesaler			
	Purchase Price	1845.93 (41.77)	2373.73 (49.85)	1836.13 (38.14)
	Marketing Cost	977.65 (22.12)	748.13 (15.71)	968.17 (20.11)
	Margin	251.00 (5.68)	251.00 (5.27)	251.00 (5.21)
4	Retailer			
	Purchase Price	3074.58 (69.58)	3372.86 (70.83)	3055.30 (63.46)
	Marketing Cost	844.28 (19.11)	889.02 (18.67)	1259.48 (26.16)
	Margin	500.00 (11.32)	500.00 (10.50)	500.00 (10.38)
5	Market Performance Indicators			
	Retail Price of Product	4418.86 (100.00)	4761.88 (100.00)	4814.78 (100.00)
	Price Spread	3227.03	3204.06	3629.29
	Producer Share in Consumer's Rupee (In Percent)	26.97	32.71	24.62
	Total Market Cost	2433.46	2433.03	2835.01
	Total Market Margin	926.00	771.03	926.00
	Marketing Efficiency	0.35	0.48	0.31

The analysis compares the marketing costs, margins, and efficiency across the Traditional, Cooperative, and Modern supply chains for mandarin oranges. In the Traditional Supply Chain, the selling price received by the farmer is ₹1,324.25 per quintal, with a marketing cost of ₹132.43, resulting in a net price of ₹1,191.83, making up 26.97% of the final retail price. The Pre-Harvester incurs marketing costs of ₹479.10 and earns a margin of ₹175, while wholesalers and retailers further add to the marketing costs, leading to a final retail price of ₹4,418.86. The price spread is the difference between the retail price and the net price received by the producer is ₹3,227.03, with a marketing efficiency of 0.35.

In the Cooperative Supply Chain, the farmer earns a higher selling price of ₹2,003.70, with marketing costs of ₹445.88, resulting in a net

price of ₹1,557.82, making up 32.71% of the final price. The FPO handles operations instead of the pre-harvester, resulting in lower marketing costs and margins. The total retail price is ₹4,761.88, with a price spread of ₹3,204.06 and a marketing efficiency of 0.48, indicating better performance.

In the Modern Supply Chain, the selling price is ₹1,317.20 with marketing costs of ₹131.72, and the net price received by the farmer is ₹1,185.49, which is 24.62% of the retail price. This chain incurs the highest marketing costs for retailers, resulting in a final retail price of ₹4,814.78. The price spread is the highest at ₹3,629.29, with a marketing efficiency of 0.31, making it the least efficient model.

4.4 Problem Faced by Mandarin Orange Producer During Marketing of Orange.

Table No 3 Market Problem of Selected Orange Producer in Three Supply Chain

Sr No	Market Problem of Producer	Traditional Supply Chain (n=20)	Cooperative Supply Chain (n=20)	Modern Supply Chain (n=20)
1	Unavailability of labour during peak season	18 (90.00)	15 (75.00)	17 (85.00)
2	Price volatility	20 (100.00)	13 (65.00)	18 (90.00)
3	High transportation cost	17 (85.00)	16 (80.00)	15 (75.00)
4	Less market access	14 (70.00)	14 (70.00)	15 (75.00)
5	Malpractices by intermediaries	12 (60.00)	4 (20.00)	12 (60.00)
6	Delay in payment	8 (40.00)	3 (15.00)	8 (40.00)

Market problems faced by Mandarin Orange producers in three different supply chains: Traditional, Cooperative, and Modern. In the Traditional Supply Chain, producers experience significant issues such as labor shortages during peak season (90%), price volatility (100%), and high transportation costs (85%). Access to markets is limited for 70% of producers, and 60% report malpractices by intermediaries. In

contrast, the Cooperative Supply Chain sees reduced problems, with fewer instances of labor shortages (75%), price volatility (65%), and intermediary malpractices (20%). The Modern Supply Chain faces challenges similar to the Traditional one, particularly in price volatility (90%), labor

availability (85%), and transportation costs (75%). However, market access remains a concern across all models, with similar percentages reporting difficulties.

Figure 1 Market Problem of Selected Orange Producer in Three Supply Chain

4.5 Problem Faced by Consumer During Purchase of Mandarin Orange.

Table No 4 Expectation of Producer from The Market in Three Supply Chain

Sr No	Problem faced by consumer	Traditional Supply Chain (N=10)	Cooperative Supply Chain (N=10)	Modern Supply Chain (N=10)
1	High price as compared to quality	10 (100.00)	8 (80.00)	9 (90.00)
2	Retailer lack sufficient packaging material unable to meet consumer demand	6 (60.00)	6 (60.00)	1 (10.00)
3	Mandarin orange is not properly weight leading to uneven quantities to consumer	7 (70.00)	6 (60.00)	0 (0.00)
4	Improper grading of mandarin orange	7 (70.00)	7 (70.00)	4 (40.00)
5	Difficulty in selecting the right mandarin orange	5 (50.00)	4 (40.00)	6 (60.00)
6	Small change in distance result in significant change in the price of mandarin orange	6 (60.00)	6 (60.00)	6 (60.00)
7	Price of mandarin orange varies as per the relationship with retailer	6 (60.00)	5 (50.00)	0 (0.00)
8	Poor refilling	4 (40.00)	3 (30.00)	9 (90.00)
9	Fewer option is available for buying mandarin orange	4 (40.00)	5 (50.00)	8 (80.00)
10	Slow checkout processes can lead to wasted time of consumer	3 (30.00)	4 (40.00)	10 (100.00)

Consumers face various challenges when purchasing mandarin oranges across different supply chains. In the Traditional Supply Chain, all consumers (100%) reported high prices relative to quality, along with issues such as improper weighing (70%), inadequate grading (70%), and price variation based on relationships with retailers (60%). The Cooperative Supply Chain saw fewer problems, but high prices (80%) and improper grading (70%) remained concerns. The Modern Supply Chain had better packaging and weighing practices but faced issues with slow checkout processes (100%) and poor product refilling (90%). Across all models, consumers experienced price fluctuations based on distance and limited purchasing options.

Conclusion

The study provides a comprehensive comparison of three supply chains for mandarin oranges—Traditional, Cooperative, and Modern—focusing on market efficiency, price spread, and challenges

faced by producers and consumers. The Traditional Supply Chain involves multiple intermediaries, resulting in higher costs at each stage, while the Cooperative Supply Chain, supported by Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs), simplifies the process and ensures better prices for producers. The Modern Supply Chain, although more advanced with consolidation centers, shows inefficiencies and higher retail-level marketing costs.

In terms of price spread and marketing efficiency, the Cooperative Supply Chain performs the best. It offers the highest producer share (32.71%) and the lowest price spread (₹3,204.06), reflecting greater efficiency. In contrast, the Traditional Chain has a lower producer share (26.97%) and a price spread of ₹3,227.03, while the Modern Chain fares the worst, with the lowest producer share (24.62%) and the highest price spread (₹3,629.29). The Marketing Efficiency Index further confirms this, with the Cooperative Chain scoring the highest

(0.48), indicating better cost management and higher returns for farmers.

Producers face challenges across all supply chains, including labor shortages and price volatility, but these issues are more severe in the Traditional and Modern chains. The Cooperative Chain shows fewer problems, as collective farming through FPOs offers more stability, reducing malpractices by intermediaries and market volatility. Consumers, on the other hand, consistently report high prices relative to product quality, with issues like improper weighing and inconsistent grading being more frequent in the Traditional and Cooperative chains.

The Modern Chain improves packaging and grading but faces inefficiencies in retail operations, including slow checkout processes and poor product refilling.

Overall, the Cooperative Supply Chain emerges as the most efficient and beneficial model, providing better returns to producers and addressing many market challenges. The Traditional and Modern chains, though prevalent, show inefficiencies in cost management and retail operations, requiring improvements to better serve both producers and consumers.

Figure 2 Problem Faced by Consumer During Purchase of Mandarin Orange

References

1. **Alzubi, E., & Noche, B. (2022, March).** Improving Sustainability of Orange Supply Chain: A System Dynamics Model to Eliminating Pre-Harvesting Loss, Increase Workers, To Improve Farmer's Profit. In Proceedings of The International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management.
2. **Akash Kumar Maurya, Dr. Ramchandra Abhishek Singh; Mayur Wajge 2022,** "Farm Business Analysis Of Krishi Vigyan Kendra Adopters And Non-Adopters In District Mau, Uttar Pradesh " Vol. XII, ISSUE XXXXIII, JULY 2022 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 148-151.
3. **Anavrat, V. (2017).** Production And Marketing Constraints of Nagpur Mandarin Growers In Madhya Pradesh. *Agric. Update*, 12(3), 443-447. DOI: 10.15740/HAS/AU/12.3/443-447.
4. **Arumugam, N., Fatimah, M. A., Chiew, E. F., & Zainalabidin, M. (2010).** Supply Chain Analysis of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables (FFV): Prospects of Contract Farming. *Agricultural Economics*, 56(9), 435-442.
5. **Baliyan, S. P., & Kgathi, D. L. (2009, June).** Production And Marketing Problems in Small Scale Horticultural Farming in Botswana. In XVI International Symposium on Horticultural Economics and Management 831 (Pp. 31-40).
6. **Balaji, P., Karthikeyan, C., & Sureshkumar, D. (2013).** A Study on Problems Faced by The Consumers and Retailers in Modern and Traditional Retail Store Outlets in India. *Internat. J. Com. & Bus. Manage*, 6(2), 268-275.
7. **Balraj, N. (2016).** Issues And Challenges in The Supply Chain of Fruits & Vegetables Sector in India: A Review. *Splint International Journal of Professionals*, 3(8), 113-118.
8. **Bante, R., Pallewar, S., & Shrey, R. (2015).** Economics Of Orange Production in Nagpur District of Maharashtra. *Internat. Res. J. Agric. Eco. & Stat.*, 6(1), 136-139.
9. **Bilewar, V. S. (2013).** Economic Analysis of Orange Nurseries in Nagpur District (Doctoral Dissertation, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra.).
10. **Bilewar, V. S. (2013).** Economic Analysis of Orange Nurseries in Nagpur District.
11. **Bidyasagar, T., & Nicra, S. R. F. (2017).** Marketing Channel and Marketing Efficiency Analysis for Rice in Nalbari District of Assam (India). *Ijcs*, 5(5), 1285-1289.
12. **Dhumale, P. M. (2017).** Constraints In Production and Marketing of Oranges.
13. **Epperson, J. E., & Estes, E. A. (1999).** Fruit And Vegetable Supply-Chain Management, Innovations, And Competitiveness: Cooperative Regional Research Project S-222. *Journal Of Food Distribution Research*, 30(3), 38-43.
14. **Gardas, B. B., Raut, R. D., & Narkhede, B. (2017).** Modelling Causal Factors of Post-Harvesting Losses in Vegetable and Fruit Supply Chain: An Indian Perspective. *Renewable And Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 80, 1355-1371.
15. **Gawande, A. (2007).** Study On Marketing Pattern of Orange in Pandhurna Block of Chhindwara.
16. **Haque, E. U., Hayat, A., Asim, M., Afzaal, S., Hanif, M. S., Murtaza, M. A., Din, A., Sabir, S., & Ahmad, S. (2022).** The Supply and Value Chain of Citrus Fruit: Producer to Consumer. In *Citrus Production* (Pp. 405-420). Crc Press.
17. **Hemambara, H. S., & Yogesh, M. (2014).** Production And Marketing Problems of Papaya Growers in North Karnataka. *Power*, 37, 37.
18. **Jaya Chandra, P. (2015).** Supply Chain Mapping and Feasibility of Establishing Collection Centres for Sweet Orange in Nalgonda District of Telangana.
19. **Kamble, P. T. (2011).** Supply Chain Management in Orange and Processed Products.
20. **Kausadikar, H. H. (2019).** Economics Of Production Marketing of Sweet Orange in Marathwada Region of Maharashtra.

21. **Kirci, M., Isaksson, O., & Seifert, R. (2022).** Managing Perishability in The Fruit and Vegetable Supply Chains. *Sustainability*, 14(9), P.5378.
22. **Ladaniya, M. S., Wanjari, V., & Mahalle, B. C. (2003).** Price Spread of Pomegranates. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 58(4), 800-811.
23. **Masudkar, D. D., Kamble, V. B., & Anarase, M. S. (2017).** Socio-Economic Status of The Farmers in Adopted Village. *Journal Of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 6(6s), 1117-1119.
24. **Meetei, D. K. D., & Singh, L. K. (2013).** Overcoming Marketing Problems of Horticultural Produces in Manipur. *International Journal in Multidisciplinary and Academic Research (Ssijmar)*, 2(5).
25. **Negi, S., & Anand, N. (2014).** Supply Chain Efficiency: An Insight from Fruits and Vegetables Sector in India. *Journal Of Operations and Supply Chain Management*, 7(2), 154-167.
26. **Negi, S., & Anand, N. (2015).** Supply Chain of Fruits & Vegetables Agribusiness in Uttarakhand (India): Major Issues and Challenges. *Journal Of Supply Chain Management Systems*, 4(1), 43-57.
27. **Purushottam, B. A. (2023).** An Economic Analysis of Production and Marketing of Mandarin Orange in Maharashtra (Doctoral Dissertation, Rpcau, Pusa).
28. **Rais, M., & Sheoran, A. (2015).** Scope of Supply Chain Management in Fruits and Vegetables in India.
29. **Rani, S., Lal, C., & Kait, R. (2022).** Marketing Costs and Price Spread for Selected Fruit Crops in Haryana State: A Study of Selected Districts. *Economic And Regional Studies/Studia Economize I Regionalne*, 15(4), 533-547.
30. **Roy, M. L., Chandra, N., Kharbikar, H. L., Joshi, P., & Jethi, R. (2013).** Socio-Economic Status of Hill Farmers: An Exploration from Almora District in Uttarakhand. *International Journal of Agriculture and Food Science Technology*, 4(4), 353-359.
31. **Sharma, S., & Upadhayaya, S. (2020).** Marketing Of Mandarin Orange in Jajarkot District: A Value Chain Analysis. *Malaysian E Commerce Journal*, 4(1), 05-08.
32. **Shekhaliya, Viraj, And Snehal Mishra. (2024).** "Analysis Of Marketing Channels of Papaya in Middle Gujarat, India". *Journal Of Experimental Agriculture International*, 46 (8): 355-363. <https://doi.org/10.9734/Jeai/2024/V46i82713>.
33. **Singh, D. K., Singh, A. K., Yadav, V. P., Singh, R. B., Baghel, R. S., & Singh, M. (2009).** Association Of Socio-Economic Status with Economic Motivation of The Farmers. *Age*, 30(35), 27.
34. **Ugale, R. D. (2017).** Economics Of Production and Marketing of Sweet Orange in Jalna District of Maharashtra State.
35. **Usha Rani, J. O. N. N. A. L. A. G. A. D. D. A. (1997).** Economic Analysis of Production and Marketing of Ber in Anantapur District Of Andhra Pradesh.